

A COMPLEX VARIABLE-VARIATIONAL METHOD ABOUT MULTI-REGIONS IN SOLUTION OF STRESS INTENSITY FACTORS FOR ANISOTROPIC PLATE WITH CRACKS

Cui Deyu and Zhang Xing

Beijing University of Aeronautics and Astronautics, 100083, China

ABSTRACT

Description is given of an analytical-variational method for determination of the stress intensity factors in anisotropic plates with unsymmetric double edge cracks. The analysis is based upon the use of the two dimensional theory of anisotropic elasticity to establish stress and displacement series which satisfy all basic equations, the condition of given resultant forces and single valued condition around the pin holes. A generalized variational principle about multi-regions is applied to satisfy the boundary conditions and interface conditions between subregions. Numerical studies reveal that the convergent results are given by a quite simple program which reduces data manipulation and computer time.

Keywords: anisotropic plates, edge cracks, stress intensity factors, analytical-variational method

1. INTRODUCTION

In order to improve the accuracy and efficiency of computation and eliminate the indeterminacy of modelling, a complex-variable variational method is presented.

2. ANALYSIS FOR STRESS AND DISPLACEMENT FIELDS

According to two-dimensional theory of anisotropic elasticity, the stress and displacement fields can be expressed¹

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \sigma_{xx} &= 2\text{Re}[\mu_1^2 \varphi'(z_1) + \mu_2^2 \psi'(z_2)] \\ \sigma_{yy} &= 2\text{Re}[\varphi'(z_1) + \psi'(z_2)] \\ \sigma_{xy} &= -2\text{Re}[\mu_1 \varphi'(z_1) + \mu_2 \psi'(z_2)] \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (1)$$

$$\left. \begin{aligned} u_x &= 2\text{Re}[p_1 \varphi(z_1) + p_2 \psi(z_2)] \\ u_y &= 2\text{Re}[q_1 \varphi(z_1) + q_2 \psi(z_2)] \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (2)$$

Fig.1 Cracked plate subjected to pin loads

in which

$$p_K = a_{11} \mu_K^2 + a_{12} - a_{16} \mu_K, \quad q_K = \frac{a_{12} \mu_K^2 + a_{22} - a_{26} \mu_K}{\mu_K} \quad (3)$$

$$z_K = x + \mu_K y = r_K \{ \cos \theta_K + i \sin \theta_K \} \quad (K = 1, 2) \quad (4)$$

with μ_K being the complex roots of the following algebraic equation

$$a_{11} \mu^4 - 2a_{16} \mu^3 + (2a_{12} + a_{66}) \mu^2 - 2a_{26} \mu + a_{22} = 0 \quad (5)$$

Now we investigate the plate with edge crack(Fig.1). The stress free boundary conditions on the crack surfaces are

$$\theta = \pm \pi, \quad \sigma_{xy} = 0, \quad \sigma_{yy} = 0 \quad (6)$$

For simplicity, the complex functions $\varphi(z_1)$ and $\psi(z_2)$ are decomposed^{2, 3}

$$\varphi(z_1) = \varphi_1(z_1) + \varphi_2(z_1); \quad \psi(z_2) = \psi_1(z_2) + \psi_2(z_2) \quad (7)$$

which satisfy the conditions $\sigma_{xy} = 0$ and $\sigma_{yy} = 0$ on the uncut portion of the cracked cross section along x-axis, respectively. Considering eq.(1), it can be found that

$$\mu_1 \varphi'_1(\tau) + \mu_2 \psi'_1(\tau) = 0, \quad \varphi'_2(\tau) + \psi'_2(\tau) = 0 \quad (8)$$

where τ represents the value of z_1 and z_2 on x-axis. By means of equations (1), (6) and (8), we have

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \varphi'_1(z_1) &= \frac{\mu_2}{\mu_2 - \mu_1} \left\{ z_1^{-\frac{1}{2}} f_1(z_1) + g_1(z_1) \right\}, \quad \varphi'_2(z_1) = \frac{1}{\mu_2 - \mu_1} \left\{ z_1^{-\frac{1}{2}} f_2(z_1) + g_2(z_1) \right\} \\ \psi'_1(z_2) &= \frac{-\mu_1}{\mu_2 - \mu_1} \left\{ z_2^{-\frac{1}{2}} f_1(z_2) + g_1(z_2) \right\}, \quad \psi'_2(z_2) = \frac{-1}{\mu_2 - \mu_1} \left\{ z_2^{-\frac{1}{2}} f_2(z_2) + g_2(z_2) \right\} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (9)$$

$$\text{where } f_n(z_K) = \sum_{m=0}^M F_{nm} z_K^m, \quad g_n(z_K) = \sum_{m=0}^M G_{nm} z_K^m \quad (10)$$

$$\text{It is evident that } F_{nm} = \overline{F_{nm}}, \quad G_{nm} = -\overline{G_{nm}} \quad (11)$$

i.e. the coefficients F_{nm} are real while G_{nm} are imaginary. For the cracked plate subjected to pin loads, the additional terms are introduced into the complex functions to consider the condition of given resultant forces and single valued condition of displacements surrounding the pin holes, that is

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \varphi(z_1) &= \sum_{n=1}^N E_{1n} \ln(z_1 - z_1^{(n)}) + \varphi_1(z_1) + \varphi_2(z_1) \\ \psi(z_2) &= \sum_{n=1}^N E_{2n} \ln(z_2 - z_2^{(n)}) + \psi_1(z_2) + \psi_2(z_2) \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (12)$$

where N is the number of pin holes and

$$z_K^{(n)} = x^{(n)} + \mu_K y^{(n)} = r_K^{(n)} (\cos \theta_K^{(n)} + i \sin \theta_K^{(n)}) \quad (13)$$

with $x^{(n)}$ and $y^{(n)}$ representing the coordinates for a point in the n th pin hole.

At first, the condition of given resultant forces at pin holes is taken to be considered. Taking free body from the plate by a cylindrical surface around the hole n (Fig.1) and projecting the forces acting on the cylindrical boundary (C_n) of the element to x - and y -axes, we have

$$\begin{aligned} R_{x_n} &= \oint_{C_n} c_n T_x ds = \oint_{C_n} c_n \frac{\partial}{\partial s} \left(\frac{\partial U}{\partial y} \right) ds \\ &= [\mu_1 \varphi(z_1) + \bar{\mu}_1 \bar{\varphi}(\bar{z}_1) + \mu_2 \psi(z_2) + \bar{\mu}_2 \bar{\psi}(\bar{z}_2)]_{C_n} = 2\pi i (E_{1n} \mu_1 - \bar{E}_{1n} \bar{\mu}_1 + E_{2n} \mu_2 - \bar{E}_{2n} \bar{\mu}_2) \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

$$\begin{aligned} R_{y_n} &= \oint_{C_n} c_n T_y ds = - \oint_{C_n} c_n \frac{\partial}{\partial s} \left(\frac{\partial U}{\partial x} \right) ds = - [\varphi(z_1) + \bar{\varphi}(\bar{z}_1) + \psi(z_2) + \bar{\psi}(\bar{z}_2)]_{C_n} \\ &= -2\pi i (E_{1n} - \bar{E}_{1n} + E_{2n} - \bar{E}_{2n}) \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

where U is the stress function. From above two equations, it can be found that

$$- \frac{R_{1n} + iR_{2n}}{2\pi} = (1 + i\mu_1)E_{1n} - (1 + i\bar{\mu}_1)\bar{E}_{1n} + (1 + i\mu_2)E_{2n} - (1 + i\bar{\mu}_2)\bar{E}_{2n} \quad (16)$$

in which R_{1n} and R_{2n} are used to represent the components of pin load.

Applying eg.(2) and eg.(12), the single valued condition of displacements becomes

$$(u_x + iu_y)|_{C_n} = (p_1 + iq_1)E_{1n} - (\bar{p}_1 + i\bar{q}_1)\bar{E}_{1n} + (p_2 + iq_2)E_{2n} - (\bar{p}_2 + i\bar{q}_2)\bar{E}_{2n} = 0 \quad (17)$$

Considering equations (16) and (17), it can be shown that for orthotropic plate

$$\mu_K = i\beta_K, \quad p_K^I = q_K^R = 0 \quad (K = 1, 2) \quad (18)$$

$$E_{1n}^R = q_2^I R_{1n} / c_1, \quad E_{1n}^I = p_2^R R_{2n} / c_2, \quad E_{2n}^R = -q_1^I R_{1n} / c_1, \quad E_{2n}^I = -p_1^R R_{2n} / c_2 \quad (19)$$

$$\text{where } c_1 = 4\pi(\beta_1 q_2^I - \beta_2 q_1^I), \quad c_2 = 4\pi(p_1^R - p_2^R) \quad (20)$$

with the superscripts R and I as the real and imaginary parts of coefficients.

Assuming $H_{1m} = F_{1m}$, $H_{2m} = -iG_{1m}$, $H_{3m} = F_{2m}$, $H_{4m} = -iG_{2m}$

and considering equations (1), (2) and (12), the stress and displacement components can be taken in the form

$$\sigma_{ij} = \sigma_{ij}^* + \sigma_{ij}^{**}, \quad u_i = u_i^* + u_i^{**} \quad (i, j = 1, 2) \quad (21)$$

with

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \sigma_{ij}^* &= \sum_{l=1}^4 \sum_{m=0}^M \lambda_{ijlm} H_{lm}, \quad u_i^* = \sum_{l=1}^4 \sum_{m=0}^M \xi_{ilm} H_{lm} \\ \sigma_{ij}^{**} &= \sum_{K=1}^2 \sum_{n=1}^N e_{ijKn} R_{Kn}, \quad u_i^{**} = \sum_{K=1}^2 \sum_{n=1}^N f_{iKn} R_{Kn} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (22)$$

where λ_{ijlm} , ξ_{ilm} , e_{ijKn} and f_{iKn} are known functions of r_K and θ_K ($K = 1, 2$) with the material constants as parameters.

3. ANALYTICAL-GENERALIZED VARIATIONAL METHOD

For investigation of the plate with unsymmetric double edge crack, the cracked plate is decomposed into two subregions with an edge crack by cut S^* (Fig2). The stress and displacement fields for each subregion can be expressed in terms of expressions (21) and (22). The determination of unknown coefficients in the series of σ_{ij}^* and u_i^* should depend upon the boundary conditions of the subregions and interface conditions between them. These conditions can be satisfied by using a generalized variational principle about multi-regions. Variational equation obtained from Lagrange's multipliers method is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \delta \Pi &= \sum_{K=1}^2 \left\{ \int_{S_{QK}} [(\tau_{ij} n_j - Q_i) \delta v_i^*]_K dS_K - \int_{S_{UK}} [(v_i - \bar{v}_i) \delta \tau_{ij}^* n_j]_K dS_K \right. \\ &+ \sum_{n=1}^N \int_{S_{nK}} [(\tau_{ij} n_j - Q_i) \delta v_i^*]_K dS_K + \int_{S_{CK}} (\tau_{ij}^{**} n_j \delta v_i^*)_K dS_K \left. \right\} + \int_{S^*} [(\tau_{ij} n_j)_1 \\ &+ (\tau_{ij} n_j)_2] (\delta v_i^*)_1 dS^* + \int_{S^*} [(v_i)_1 - (v_i)_2] (\delta \tau_{ij}^* n_j)_2 dS^* = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

in which v_i , τ_{ij} , Q_i and n_j are the displacement, stress, surface traction and direction cosine components, respectively, S_{QK} and S_{UK} the boundaries where Q_i and v_i are prescribed, respectively, S_{nK} ($n = 1, 2, \dots, N$) the surfaces of pin holes and S_{CK} the crack surfaces. Here, the subscript K denotes the subregion concerned. All of the field quantities are described by the global coordinate system (x - y). For the cases of small pin diameters, the variation δv^* can be considered as unchanged along the hole surface. Then, due to the availability of eq.(16), the following term in eq.(23) may be reduced as

$$\int_{S_{nK}} [(\tau_{ij} n_j - Q_i) \delta v_i^*]_K dS_K = \left\{ \int_{S_{nK}} (\tau_{ij} n_j - Q_i)_K dS_K \right\} (\delta v_i^*)_K = 0 \quad (24)$$

Suppose that there is no displacement boundary S_{UK} and loading system is in self-equilibrium. It is instructive to decompose the problem to be solved into two states: the loaded plate with crack tips held (state $\langle \alpha \rangle$) and unloaded plate with crack tip displacements (Δ_1

and Δ_2) along x - axis (state $\langle \beta \rangle$) shown in Fig.2. Each plate is divided into two subregions as indicated above.

At first, the state $\langle \alpha \rangle$ is taken to be considered, due to the relation between the global and the local coordinate systems for each subregion, we have

$$\left. \begin{aligned} (v_i)_1 &= (u_i)_1, & (\tau_{ij})_1 &= (\sigma_{ij})_1, & (Q_i)_1 &= (P_i)_1, & (n_i)_1 &= (m_i)_1 \\ (v_i)_2 &= -(u_i)_2, & (\tau_{ij})_2 &= (\sigma_{ij})_2, & (Q_i)_2 &= -(P_i)_2, & (n_i)_2 &= (m_i)_2 \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (25)$$

in which $(u_i)_K$, $(\sigma_{ij})_K$, $(P_i)_K$ and $(m_i)_K$ are the displacement, stress, traction and direction cosine components with respect to subregion K in local coordinate system ($x_1 - y_1$ or $x_2 - y_2$), respectively. Considering eq. (24) and substituting eq. (25) into eq. (23), the variation equation referred to local coordinate systems becomes

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{K=1}^2 \int_{S_{\alpha K}} (\sigma_{ij}^* m_j \delta u_i^*)_K dS_K + \int_{S^*} [(\sigma_{ij}^* m_j)_1 - (\sigma_{ij}^* m_j)_2] (\delta u_i^*)_1 dS^* \\ & - \int_{S^*} [(u_i^*)_1 + (u_i^*)_2] (\delta \sigma_{ij}^* m_j)_2 dS^* = \sum_{K=1}^2 \int_{S_{\alpha K}} (P_i \delta u_i^*)_K dS_K - \sum_{K=1}^2 \int_{S_{\alpha K}} (\sigma_{ij}^{**} m_j \delta u_i^*)_K dS_K \\ & - \int_{S^*} [(\sigma_{ij}^{**} m_j)_1 - (\sigma_{ij}^{**} m_j)_2] (\delta u_i^*)_1 dS^* + \int_{S^*} [(u_i^{**})_1 + (u_i^{**})_2] (\delta \sigma_{ij}^* m_j)_2 dS^* \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

Substituting eq. (22) into above equation, the algebraic equations about the unknown coefficients $(H_{lm}^{(\alpha)})_K$ can be established. Thus, the stress intensity factors for state $\langle \alpha \rangle$ are given by

$$K_{IK}^{(\alpha)} = 2\sqrt{2\pi} (H_{10}^{(\alpha)})_K, \quad K_{IIK}^{(\alpha)} = 2\sqrt{2\pi} (H_{30}^{(\alpha)})_K \quad (27)$$

and the resultant $R_1^{(\alpha)}$ of the stresses $\sigma_{ij}^{(\alpha)}$ on S^* is

$$R_1^{(\alpha)} = \int_{S^*} (\sigma_{ij}^{(\alpha)} m_j)_1 dS^* \quad (28)$$

Next, for state $\langle \beta \rangle$, the field quantities associated with the global and the local coordinate systems are related by the following equations

$$\left. \begin{aligned} (v_i)_1 &= (u_i)_1 + \delta_{i1} \Delta_1, & (\tau_{ij})_1 &= (\sigma_{ij})_1, & (Q_i)_1 &= 0, & (n_i)_1 &= (m_i)_1 \\ (v_i)_2 &= -(u_i)_2 + \delta_{i1} \Delta_2, & (\tau_{ij})_2 &= (\sigma_{ij})_2, & (Q_i)_2 &= 0, & (n_i)_2 &= -(m_i)_2 \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (29)$$

Similarly, the variational equation can be obtained in the form

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{K=1}^2 \int_{S_{\alpha K}} (\sigma_{ij}^* m_j \delta u_i^*)_K dS_K + \int_{S^*} [(\sigma_{ij}^* m_j)_1 - (\sigma_{ij}^* m_j)_2] (\delta u_i^*)_1 dS^* \\ & - \int_{S^*} [(u_i^*)_1 + (u_i^*)_2] (\delta \sigma_{ij}^* m_j)_2 dS^* = 2\Delta \int_{S^*} \delta (\sigma_{ij}^* m_j)_2 dS^* \end{aligned} \quad (30)$$

in which $2\Delta = \Delta_1 - \Delta_2$, Let $\Delta = 1.0$, the coefficients $(H_{lm}^{(\beta)})_K$ can be obtained by solving eq. (30). Then, the S.I.F. and resultant of $\sigma_{ij}^{(\beta)}$ on S^* are found to be

$$K_{IK}^{(\beta)} = 2\sqrt{2\pi} (H_{10}^{(\beta)})_K, \quad K_{IIK}^{(\beta)} = 2\sqrt{2\pi} (H_{30}^{(\beta)})_K, \quad R_1^{(\beta)} = \int_{S^*} (\sigma_{ij}^{(\beta)} m_j)_1 dS^* \quad (31)$$

According to the principle of superposition, it is seen that

$$R_1 = R_1^{(\alpha)} + R_1^{(\beta)} \Delta \quad (32)$$

where R_1 is the total force along x-direction on the cut S^* . With the aid of eq. (32), the relative displacement of two crack tips (2Δ) is found and the stress intensity factors of the cracked plate are given by

$$K_{IK} = K_{IK}^{(\alpha)} + K_{IK}^{(\beta)} \Delta, \quad K_{IIK} = K_{IIK}^{(\alpha)} + K_{IIK}^{(\beta)} \Delta \quad (33)$$

4. NUMERICAL EXAMPLES

The forementioned approach can be used to evaluate the stress intensity factors for both orthotropic and isotropic plates with double edge cracks. In isotropic case, a small amount ε is introduced to make

$$\mu_1 = i\beta_1 = (1 - \varepsilon)i, \quad \mu_2 = i\beta_2 = (1 + \varepsilon)i \quad (34)$$

Where ε tends to zero, it can be shown that the stress and displacement functions turn to those given by the isotropic theory. To verify the reliability of the results, as a comparison of relative accuracy, the problem of a symmetric double edge crack under uniform axial tension appear in Fig.3 is investigated. Table 1 lists the numerical results of the normalized S.I.F. $\bar{K}_I = K_I / (\sigma\sqrt{\pi a})$. The maximum difference in the results obtained by this method is less than 1 percent when compared with the finding of earlier studies⁵. Fig.4 depicts the non-symmetric edge cracks near notch in a finite plate subjected to pin loads. The curves of dimensionless S.I.F. $\bar{K}_I = K_I \sqrt{W} / P$ versus crack length are shown in Fig.5. Table 2 presents the convergency of S.I.F. results \bar{K}_I for the cracked plate shown in Fig.4 where the material constants are $E_{11} = 144.8\text{GPa}$, $E_{22} = 11.7\text{GPa}$, $G_{12} = 9.7\text{GPa}$ and $\gamma_{12} = 0.21$.

Fig.2 Model of investigation of a plate with unsymmetric double edge crack

Fig.3 Plate with symmetric double edge crack under uniform axial tension

Fig.4 Plate with a double edge crack near notch subjected to pin loads

Fig.5 Plot of normalized S.I.F. $K_1 = K_1 \sqrt{2W} / P$ against non-dimensional crack length a_1 / W for $H / W = 1.0$, $a_2 / W = 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5$, $c / H = 0.3$

Table 1 Normalized S.I.F. $\bar{K}_I = K_I / (\sigma\sqrt{\pi a})$ for the plate with a double edge crack under uniform axial tension

a / W	This method	Ref.5
0.1	1.14	1.13
0.2	1.17	1.16
0.3	1.23	1.23
0.4	1.28	1.28
0.5	1.33	1.33
0.6	1.39	1.38

Table 2 Convergency of numerical solution for a double edge crack near notch in orthotropic plate subjected to pin loads (Fig.4)

(H / W = 1.0, R / W = 0.1, b / W = 0.2, C / H = 0.5, a₁ = a₂ = a)

M \ a / W	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6
4	0.878	1.008	1.154	1.324	1.521	1.749
5	0.870	0.997	1.134	1.294	1.504	1.794
6	0.884	1.020	1.167	1.332	1.550	1.828
7	0.882	1.006	1.131	1.290	1.512	1.992
8	0.870	1.013	1.156	1.320	1.547	1.962
9	0.874	1.012	1.157	1.321	1.551	1.965
10	0.878	1.011	1.151	1.316	1.544	1.958

Reference

- 1.Lekhnitskii, S.G., Theory of Elasticity of an Anisotropic Body, English Translation, Mir Publisher, 1981.
- 2.Sih, G. C. and Chen, E. P., Mech of Fracture 6, Martinus Nijhoff Publishers, 1981, pp.9–22.
- 3.Gu Pei and Zhang Xing, ACTA MATERIALE COMPOSITAE SINICA, 2(1)pp. 63, 1985.
- 4.Washizu, K., Variational Methods in Elasticity and Plasticity, Second Edition, Pergamon Press, 1975, pp.27–48.
5. Hellen, T.K., On the Method of Virtual Crack Extension, Int. J. Numer. Method Eng. 9, pp.187–207, 1975.